

ELASTIC BEHAVIOR AND FRACTURE RESPONSE OF BRITTLE-MATRIX PARTICULATE COMPOSITES: MODELING VS. EXPERIMENTS

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ABSTRACT: Particle-reinforced glass-matrix composites have been characterized by means of the numerical model OOF. Two types of composites were considered, containing either Al₂O₃ platelets or Mo particles. OOF is a computational tool which maps the material microstructure, such as a digitized micrograph of the composite cross section, onto a finite element mesh. Therefore all microstructural details, including particle shape, orientation, dimension as well as volume fraction, can be included in the microstructural model. The OOF finite element solver can be used in conjunction with selected failure criteria suitable for brittle fracture in order to determine the critical load for fracture initiation and to investigate crack propagation. For the Al₂O₃ platelet reinforced composite material, the fracture characteristics, in particular toughening mechanisms, were investigated by means of the numerical approach and compared with available experimental results. Thermal residual stresses that arise upon cooling from the processing temperature due to the thermal expansion coefficients mismatch between matrix and reinforcements were determined for both composites. The possible toughening mechanisms in Mo/glass composites are discussed. The results of the present study demonstrate the applicability of the OOF model to characterise fracture behaviour of glass matrix composites and the potential of its use in the design of such composites containing either ceramic or metallic particles as reinforcement.

KEYWORDS: glass matrix composites, modeling, brittle fracture, finite element method, toughening

INTRODUCTION

Glass is a candidate material for several technical applications due to its interesting optical, electrical and thermal insulating properties. However, its brittleness and flaw sensitivity limit its usage as a structural material. In order to avoid catastrophic failure of glass components, it is possible to form composite materials, i.e. to reinforce the glass either with fibers or discontinuous reinforcement such as platelets, whiskers and particulates [1-3]. An important aspect of the design and development of glass matrix composites is to be able to predict the mechanical properties and fracture behaviour of the materials from microstructural information. Computational approaches are very attractive in this regard, as they may be conveniently developed as predictive tools thus becoming a very useful aid for composite design.

In this work, we illustrate the application of a finite-element based numerical model, called OOF [4], in the characterisation of two different glass-matrix particulate composites, which have been developed and experimentally characterised in previous research efforts. The composites contain either ceramic [5,6] or metallic [7] inclusions in a borosilicate glass matrix.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Two types of glass matrix composites are considered: i) borosilicate (DURAN® Schott Glas, Germany) glass matrix reinforced with Al₂O₃ platelets [5,6] and ii) the same borosilicate glass matrix reinforced with Mo particles [7]. Relevant properties of the composite constituents are given in Table 1. In previous experimental work, it was found that 30vol% platelet addition increased the fracture

toughness of the glass matrix in about 3 times [5,6], while 10 vol% Mo particle addition led to an increase of fracture toughness of about 20% [7].

Table 1. Relevant properties of the composite constituents [5-7]

	Matrix Borosilicate glass (DURAN®, Schott Glass)	Ceramic inclusions Al ₂ O ₃ platelets	Metallic inclusions Mo particles
Thermal expansion coefficient (°C ⁻¹ 10 ⁻⁶)	3.3	8.9	5.1
Young's modulus (GPa)	63	400	336
Poisson's ratio	0.22	0.25	0.31

Numerical method

Both composites were analysed by means of the OOF numerical model [4], focussing on residual thermal stresses and crack propagation behaviour. OOF is a microstructure based finite element code able to convert digitized images of microstructures onto finite element meshes. Therefore all microstructural details, such as particle shape, dimension and volume fraction, can be taken into account in the numerical model and therefore their effect on the overall mechanical behavior of the materials can be assessed. The OOF code has been exploited to study the mechanical and fracture properties of a wide range of heterogeneous and composite materials, including platelet-reinforced composites, thermal barrier coatings, iron titanate, aluminum-silicon alloys, polycrystalline alumina and porous glasses [8-13]. Cannillo and Carter have used OOF to determine the reliability of composite and heterogeneous microstructures [14], damage accumulation in complex microstructures [15] and the fracture behaviour of graded materials [16]. Of relevance for the present investigation, recently, the OOF code has been used to determine crack propagation and damage accumulation in Al₂O₃ platelet reinforced glass matrix composites [17,18]. The OOF code is adopted here to set up a reliable model for the characterisation of the two composite systems described above. To this aim, finite element grids were obtained starting from SEM micrographs of the two materials and the mechanical behavior was analyzed. In particular, the finite element solver was used with selected failure criteria implemented inside the OOF code in order to investigate crack initiation and propagation in both composites. Also thermal residual stresses were calculated using OOF.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. The alumina-glass composite

Samples with 30% vol. Al₂O₃ platelets were considered, which showed an increment in the fracture toughness of ~ 3 over the glass matrix [5,6]. This improvement was ascribed mainly to two concurrent phenomena: the presence of compressive thermal residual stresses in the brittle glass matrix and a crack deflection mechanism; both effects were confirmed experimentally [5,6]. The thermal stresses arise upon cooling from the processing temperature and are due to the thermal expansion coefficient (TEC) mismatch between the matrix and the inclusions (see Table 1). These residual thermal stresses were experimentally measured by fluorescence spectroscopy [6].

In order to numerically analyze thermal residual stresses in Al₂O₃ platelet reinforced glass matrix composites, a model based on the OOF code was prepared and applied, as presented elsewhere [17,18]. The study confirmed the existence of compressive stresses in the matrix and tensile stresses in the particles, as experimentally measured. The magnitude of residual stresses was shown to depend on the volume fraction of platelets. The higher the platelet content, the higher was the compression stress in the glass matrix. This compression has a favorable effect on the strength of the composite: when an external tension is applied, the compression must be completely unloaded before the solicitation may become critical for fracture initiation. In Figure 1, compressive residual stresses arising in the matrix for platelet volume fraction of 30%, as calculated by the numerical method, are shown: the compression stress presents its maximum at the interface between the matrix and the particles.

Figure 1. Residual thermal stresses arising upon cooling from the processing temperature in a glass matrix composite reinforced with alumina platelets, calculated using the OOF code.

Microscopy observation of fractured surfaces pointed out that a mechanism of crack deflection occurred during composite fracture, however only for certain orientations between the platelet and the advancing crack direction [5,6]. For angles of intersection lower than 50° the deflection mechanism was shown to be active. Crack/platelet interaction was investigated also by means of the numerical model [18]. The finite element solver was used in conjunction with the Griffith's criterion for brittle fracture, i.e. the elements are designed to fail when the criterion is met. In this way, it is possible to track crack propagation and to study the interaction between the crack and the reinforcements. For these calculations, K_{IC} was set equal to $0.77 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$ for the glass matrix and to $1.76 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$ for the alumina platelets. The computational simulations, in agreement with the experimental results [5], confirmed that the particle was fractured for angles larger than 50° , whilst the crack deflection occurred for lower angles. In Figure 2, a typical example of crack deflection for a glass/alumina platelet sample is shown: the crack does not intersect the platelet, its path is deviated leading to the crack deflection mechanism, as experimentally confirmed [5,6].

Moreover, the effect of the platelets dimension was investigated for the assessment of the fracture behavior. It is well known from the literature that spontaneous crack nucleation in two-phase materials occurs only if a critical size of inclusions is reached [19]. Therefore, the critical size for fracture initiation in the present composites was investigated by means of the numerical model. To this aim, a very simple geometry was analyzed: a single alumina platelet embedded in the glass matrix. Calculations with increasing platelet size, ranging from 5 to 30 μm , were carried out. Figure 3 illustrates the results of this part of the study. Smaller platelets, with a dimension of up to 25 μm , were fractured and no microcrack appeared at the platelet tip (cases a), b), c) of Figure 3). When the critical dimension of 25 μm is reached, however, cracks nucleate at platelet edges as Figure 3d) shows. Therefore, in order to avoid spontaneous microcracking the average size of the alumina inclusions in this particular composite should be kept below the critical dimension of 25 μm . For the fabrication of the investigated materials, alumina platelets were selected in the range 5-25 μm and no spontaneous crack generation was observed, in agreement with the numerical results. Thus, the model can be considered a reliable tool for the design of brittle matrix particulate composites, in order to avoid phenomena of spontaneous microcracking. This is particularly crucial when the composite is intended for structural applications. The presented results demonstrate the suitability of the OOF code to investigate the fracture behaviour of ceramic particulate reinforced brittle matrix composites, which includes the assessment of toughening mechanisms, microcracking behaviour and effect of residual thermal stresses on crack propagation. The numerical findings are in close agreement with

experimental results in the alumina platelet reinforced glass matrix composites considered. Therefore, the OOF code can be used to design new brittle-matrix composite materials: the constituent materials, for example, can be selected on the basis of their thermoelastic properties, in order to achieve a favorable residual stress field in both phases. The size and orientation of inclusions can be chosen depending on the direction of the applied load in each particular application considered.

Figure 2. Crack deflection in a glass matrix composite reinforced by Al_2O_3 platelets (represented by ellipses), as determined by OOF (in black fractured elements). Note that the angle of intersection between the crack direction and the particle is equal to 0° in this example.

2. The molybdenum-glass composite

For analysing the Mo/borosilicate glass matrix composites, a finite element grid was constructed starting from a SEM micrograph of the material cross section. The computational mesh was subjected to thermal load in order to simulate cooling of the composite from the fabrication temperature. The upper temperature is however taken as the glass transition temperature of the glass (i.e. 530°C) since thermal residual stresses will not relax after reaching this temperature during cooling. As in the alumina platelet/glass composites analysed above, a tensile stress developed in the particles and a compression stress in the glass matrix. However, the magnitude of the compressive stress is not as high as in the previous case, as can be inferred from the comparison of Figures 1 and 4. This is the consequence of the relatively low mismatch of TEC between the glass matrix and the Mo particles. Therefore, the toughening effect of the residual stress field is expected to be lower in the Mo/glass composite, in comparison to the alumina/glass composite. In fact, the Mo/glass composites were originally designed to have low residual thermal stresses, in order to assure that cracks would propagate unimpeded through the matrix and particles [7]. In metal particle reinforced brittle matrix composites, the intention is to maximise the interaction of advancing cracks with the particles and so to exploit the plastic deformation of the metallic particles to enhance toughness.

Figure 3. Effect of particle size on microcracking behaviour in alumina platelet reinforced glass matrix composites for different platelet sizes (max. dimension), as determined by OOF computations: a) 5 μm , b) 10 μm c) 20 μm d) 30 μm . For particle size $> 25 \mu\text{m}$, microcrack nucleation at the particle edge is observed (d).

The fracture behavior of Mo/glass composite was investigated using the OOF code in order to allow comparison with experimental observations. The first problem was to determine the *in-situ* fracture toughness of the metallic particles, that has to be inserted in the numerical model. The approach presented in ref. [20] for the alumina-glass composite was adopted here to determine the value of K_{IC} of molybdenum particles. It was found that a value of $\sim 2.10 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$ was suitable for the present composite. This result is similar to the one experimentally determined in ref. [7]: in that work, the value of the fracture energy γ was estimated to be 7 J/m^2 , which corresponds to a value of K_{IC} equal to $2.17 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$ and thus it is in good agreement with the numerical computations. With this K_{IC} value for Mo inclusions, the present composite can be numerically investigated starting from very simple geometry, constituted by a single inclusion embedded in the glass matrix.

This composite material is the focus of current research. In particular, it is interesting to study numerically the fracture paths and crack/particle interactions in these materials. This would enable to analyze accurately the overall effect of the ductile inclusions on fracture toughness increment in the composites. In the experimental investigation [7], it was mentioned that plastic deformation of the Mo particles was only partially responsible for the measured increase in fracture toughness. The numerical investigation using OOF may be useful to ascertain the real effect of plastic deformation on toughness taking into account the constraining effect that the rigid elastic glass matrix imposes on the effective ductility of the Mo particles.

Figure 4 Thermal residual stresses in a Mo/glass composite sample, as calculated by the code OOF, on a real microstructural image of the composite containing 30 vol% inclusions.

CONCLUSIONS

Both ceramic (alumina platelets) and metallic (Mo) inclusions can be added to glass matrices to produce composites with improved fracture toughness. The finite element based numerical model OOF was shown to be applicable to both types of composites to determine residual thermal stresses and crack/inclusion interactions. This numerical code, which maps materials microstructures onto finite element grids, enables to represent the actual composite features: thus the effect of the reinforcement on the global mechanical behavior can be fully investigated. The results presented in this paper are examples on how the OOF code can be used to aid the design and optimization of brittle matrix composite materials reinforced with ceramic or metallic particulate inclusions.

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